

UNVEILING THE BRITISH PERIOD BUILT HERITAGE, A LIVING ARCHAEOLOGY IN LYALLPUR AND IN GENERAL PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This paper was presented in international conference at Faisalabad, which emphasis the British raj Architecture in Faisalabad in particular and in general Pakistan, Lyallpur was the planned city during British raj, the city got named behind the Sir James Broadwood Lyall, the British lieutenant governor of the Punjab, in 1898 Lyallpur was declared as Municipality of lower Chenab region. Lyallpur name was changed in 1973 behind the name of Saudi king Faisal bin Abdul Aziz Al Saud, Faisalabad is the third populated and largest city of Pakistan with population of 3.8 million of peoples. During British raj the multiple architectural projects were laid for regional sustainable development, in irrigation the number of barrages, bridges were constructed which resulted in vast land area cultivable to meet grain requirements. Railway stations, Railway tracks, railway track bridges were constructed for smooth and hassle free travel, Municipality and other marvelous administrative buildings were constructed for developing markets, business and raising the urban life standards, all this played a pivotal role in revenue generation. Lyallpur also owned variety of British raj Architecture; salient splendid examples are like Chenab club 1910, the most famous the clock tower in 1903, Gumti water fountain 1897, Sir James Lyal Monument, Faisal Abad railway station 1896, Sikh Gurdwara 1911. More than 15 British raj buildings are in Karachi, Sukkur and Hyderabad has variety of British Raj buildings with marvelous architectural styles, which are still functional and in use, there wouldn't be any exaggeration to call it as British period living archaeology, though the buildings in Faisal Abad and in rest of Indo-Pak region were constructed by the Britishers, but now all that are the integral part of Pakistani cultural heritage.

Keywords: Lyallpur British raj architecture, British raj architecture in general, British period heritage as living archaeology.

Methodology:

for accomplishing this research paper the author has gone through primary and secondary source of data collection, for getting first hand data the author has visited the British raj built heritage like Sukkur bridge, Khairpur and Sukkur railway stations, Lansdowne bridge sukkur bridge over Indus at Kotri and building of High court at Karachi. Articles and books are also the secondary part of data collection.

Introduction / early history of Lyallpur

The regions of shahdara, Jhang, Sandalbar Toba Tek singh, Shangla were populated and spread on waste area, which was considerably known as largest village settlement before colonial period in Punjab, which later on paved the way for founding a well-planned city during British Raj in 1880. Rai Bahadur Bhavani Das sikka played very important role in settling this new well-planned city. In 1858, the entire Punjab was governed by British raj; British Raj came with worth full Schemes of digging canals to irrigate

the waste areas. Establishment of Chenab colony brought revolution in irrigation by increasing the agricultural yields.

Map location of Lyallpur during British Raj, Source: pakgeotagging.blogspot.com

Unveiling the British period built heritage in Lyallpur

After the Cities of Indus Civilizations, the City of Lyallpur was planned city during British Raj, The great maneuvering behind planning was of Pham Young the Colonization officer, the town map /plan was on the pattern of Union Jack,

Eight road side bazars were constructed, which gave access to other regions of Punjab, Lyallpur was annexed through railway line to Wazerabad in 1895, Adjoining regions, like Gujranwala, Jhang and Montgomery were annexed as Tehsil of Lyallpur in 1896, finally in 1904 Lyallpur was declared as district.

Aerial view of Faisalabad (Lyallpur city plane on Union jack flag pattern)

Source: www.bing.com

I. **Clock Tower.** Lyallpur along with other magnificent colonial architectural buildings, the grandeur of clock tower is still prominent and intact, Sir James Lyell's decision of constructing a clock tower in center of planned city was honored by Sir Charles Montgomery Rivaz (Lieutenant Governor of Punjab) who put the foundation of majestic clock tower in recognition of crown rule and the clock tower was completed in 1905. The design of clock tower was made by Ganga Ram the prominent architect, the fascinating clock tower was made with red sand stone bricks, the source area of raw of material was Sangla Hill. The clock tower has

four levels with height of 30 meters. Tower has Square base with long arches, with ornate balconies and intricate patterns carved into the sandstone in Indo-Saracenic architectural style. Almost 11 clock towers were constructed in Pakistan during British raj. Cunningham clock tower, Peshawar 1900, Merewether Tower, 1892 Silver Jubilee clock Karachi 1935, Empress Market Karachi 1889, Clock tower Faisalabad 1905, Clock tower Sialkot 1922, Est court clock tower Gujranwala 1906, GCU Tower Lahore 1864, clock tower Multan 1884, Naval Rai Market clock tower Hyderabad 1914.

Lyallpur clock tower, source: [www.google image.com](http://www.google.com)

II. **Faisalabad Railway Station.** Faisalabad railway station was established in 1896; earlier the railway line was laid between Lyallpur and Jaranwala only, now it works as main railway line to Karachi, Lahore, Rawalpindi, Islamabad Quetta and Peshawar. The architectural design

and outlook of railway station is of western architecture of Victorian era with Greek style of long and small pillars supporting the edifice, arched windows with red bricks, high ceiling height shows the influence of Victorian architectural styles.

Faisalabad Railway Station Source: www.google.image

III. Gumti water fountain: Gumti water fountain is also popularly known as Gumti square, that is a very well persevered British raj monument constructed in 1930s, this British period fountain is combination of Victorian and Mughal architecture with ornate details and intricate stone carvings, The statue of Queen

Victoria was erected in center of fountain, later on statue was removed. This cultural icon of the Faisalabad has undergone numerous restoration episodes to keep intact its cultural and architectural glory, this (Anglo Islamic) architecture has white marble stair steps up to rooftop.

Gumti waterfountain

Source: www.google.image

IV. Memorial of Sir James Lyall: The memorial of Sir James Lyall was made in recognition of his untiring efforts and contribution he made in development of Lyallpur in 1920 after his demise in 1916 near to clock tower in company bagh, the architecture of memorial is amalgamation of Victorian and

Islamic architectural features like minarets, large dome with intricate stone carving, many of architectural features of memorial are still missing including the inscription panel written on it “In memory of Sir James Lyall, KCSI Lieutenant Governor of the Punjab, 1887-1892. Died 1916”

Memorial of Sir James Lyall, source: www.google image.com

V. **Qaisary Gate:** Qaisary gate was constructed as grand entrance of well-planned eight bazars and clock tower under the British raj in 1897. The name of gate is derived from the Urdu language word “Qaisar” which means

“Emperor” to honor the Crown rule, (in commemoration of the 60th year of the reign of Queen Victoria) Qaisary gate exhibits Victorian and Mughal architectural style with intricate stone carving with onion domes.

Qaisary gate, Source: www.google.image.com

Front view of Qisary gate with inscription in recognition of Queen Victoria

VI. **Chenab Club:** For Promoting cultural, architectural and social spaces during colonial era the credit goes to British raj for establishing the institutes and social Clubs, In Lyallpur first social club was established during (1904-1906 by Mr Henry Cus, Later on the Chenab club was established by Captain Douglis in 1910 in

company Bagh, Chenab club has Victorian architecture with Mughal influence, the arches, ornate stone carving, columns and interior with high ceiling, wooden floor with beautiful furniture. Since 1910 up-to-date the Chenab club promotes, sports, social and Cultural activities in the region.

front view of Chenab club, Source:www.google image.com

VII. Singh Sabha Gurdawara

The exact calenderical year of singh Sabha Gurdawara's construction is not clear but the most researchers has consensus on the year of its construction is about 1915, but the extention work of gurdawara may add more years to it. Singh Sabha Gurdawara is complex of three

buildings, Gurdawara, Guest house and School with multiple class rooms and halls. The architecture of Gurdawara is blend of Mughal and Sikh architecture prominently with high ceilings, minerates, largedomes, arches, pillars, inside of gurdawara is adorned with frescos, paintings, sikh symbols and intricate carvings.

Gurdawara Singh Sabha, Faisalabad

British raj heritage in Pakistan as living Archaeology

(Randomly selected British raj architectural examples)

Railway stations.

British Raj paid heed to improve and fasten the communication sources to ease & facilitate the masses and economy at maximum level. In 1855 railway service was begun, initially the short distance cities and towns were annexed, Later on; the private railway companies were encouraged to operate railway transportations to far away destinations. The salient railway operating companies were like Scinde Railway, Punjab railway, Delhi railway. Indus Flotilla,

(some of companies were merged) Indus Valley State railway, Punjab Northern state railway, Sind-sagar railway, Sindh-Pishin, Kandhar state railway and Trans Baluchistan railway.

Mr. Henry Bartle Frere the commissioner of Sindh started the survey for laying railway line in 1858. This distance of 174 km from Karachi to Kotri was completed on 13 May 1861. In result of scinde act of 1855 Punjab railways was established, like Karachi - Kotri, Multan to Lahore, the first passenger trains were moved through Indus steam Flotilla.

Fortified Northwestern Railway Bridge over the Indus at Attock

Map of North western railway during British Raj, Source: google.com

Canals & Barrages

Like other developments, massive agricultural developmental planes were initiated for sustainable and surplus agricultural yield, Barrages were constructed to provide water in all seasons, and Canals were remodeled for

perennial water flow. Irrigation bungalows, canal guardrooms are still intact and are fine example of living Archaeology.

Courts and Municipalities

Karachi Port trust

The marvelous building of K.P.T was constructed to fascinate the visitors at Karachi port city. This splendid architectural designer architect of this building was George Wittet and the building was inaugurated by Marquess of willington, the governor of Bombay on 5 January 1916. Grandeur of building was enhanced with yellow Stones brought from Jaipur that further captivated the visitors with Roman architectural style.

High Court of Sindh

The George Wittet, A.J.A Illingworth and woods Hill were the architecture designers of Indo Saracenic style Building of Sindh High Court during 1923-29, the building was inaugurated by the governor of Bombay Frederic Hugh sykes.

Lahore

Number of British Raj churches, Educational Institutes were constructed in Lahore, like Pakistan Cathedral Church Lahore 1887, Saint Anthony church 1899, Cathedral of scand Heart of Jesus 1903, Mayo School of Art (NCA), Government College, Punjab University Lahore Museum.

Lahore High Court: The iconic building of Lahore High Court was established on Mall road in 1882.

Dak Bunglow Originally Built in 1875 in the British's era, situated in Changla Gali of the Galiyat Division Khyber Pukhtoonkhwa.

Chief Minister House Nathiagali, also known as the KPK HOUSE, is the Colonial Style building built in late 1800s by the British Raj to serve as the official residency of CM.

Socio economic impact of British raj architecture

British raj architecture has highly influenced the socio-economic scenario of Pakistan, crown rule showcased the blend of architectural styles like Victorian, gothic and Mughal styles. Barrages, canals, bazars, municipalities, public administration has worthful contribution in Pakistan's economy. The construction of gigantic buildings during British raj influenced

the contemporary architecture in the region and expedited the urbanization; construction of educational buildings has fully contributed in educational landscape. Shortly, British raj buildings are national pride depicting country's history, culture and architectural diversity.

Conclusions

After the arrival and expansion of crown rule in south Asian sub-continent, an era of prosperity and development got started. Myriad public projects were initiated to consolidate the governance, mainly the irrigation, transportation and public administration sectors were under focused for viable & sustainable economy and good governance. Along with digging of new canals the existing canals were remodeled, barrages and bridges were constructed to make new land cultivable and roads to market to ease & increase the production to meet the food requirements, administrative and public sector infrastructure was erected, Baroque, gothic and neoclassical were the most prominent architectural styles during British Raj, that can be seen in the Buildings like Mereweather clock tower, frere hall, St Patrick's cathedral in Karachi and Montgomery hall in Lahore. Combining European and Islamic features a new architectural style emerged known as Indo-Saracenic style, such architectural buildings are Islamia College Peshawar, Lahore Museum, University of Punjab and King Edward medical college in Punjab.

Such splendid buildings of Municipalities, educational institutes, trade and commerce, Railways, Churches and memorials, which are still intact and plenty of them are under in use up-to-date. The stability and architectural grandeur of British raj buildings has no match after passing more than a century. According to Pakistan, antiquity act of 1979 anything, which is older than 75 years, is declared as antiquity, all mentioned British raj architectural remains are still functioning and are considered as living archaeology. For doing all this for the peoples of Indian subcontinent, we should be grateful to great minds of British raj for making this part to our historical and cultural heritage.

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